

Excess refractive index, polarizability, polarization and the molar volume of some mixed solvents

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The refractive indices and the densities of (1) protic-protic solvent mixtures (ethanol-*n*-propanol, ethanol-*n*-butanol and *n*-propanol-water), (2) aprotic-protic solvent mixtures (DMSO-DMF, DMSO-DI (1,4-dioxane) and DMF-DI) and (3) aprotic-protic solvent mixtures (DMSO, DI-methanol, ethanol, *n*-propanol and *n*-butanol) were measured experimentally at different temperatures. From the values of the measured refractive indices and the densities, the excess refractive indices, the atomic polarizations, the molar refractions, the molar volumes, the solvated radii and the polarizabilities of the mentioned mixed solvents were calculated and discussed. The results showed that, the solvent-solvent interaction reaches maximum value at definite mole fraction of each solvent depending on the nature of the solvent. Also the excess refractive indices, the densities and the atomic polarizations were found to decrease as the temperature increase. On the other hand, the molar volumes, the solvated radii, the molar refractions and the polarizabilities were found to increase as the temperature increases.

Refractive index and density measurements were expected to shed some light on both the solvent-solvent interaction¹⁻³ and the configuration⁴ of the mixed solvents. Many authors have used these properties to study the structure and the solvent-solvent interaction of binary mixtures with water⁵, aliphatic alcohols^{6,7} and cyclic ethers⁸⁻¹⁰.

The aim of the present work is to determine the excess refractive indices, the molar volumes, the polarizabilities, the polarization and the solvated radii for some protic-protic, aprotic-protic and aprotic-protic solvent mixtures at different temperatures. The mentioned physical parameters of the solvent have their importance in studying the solvation processes^{11,12}.

Results and discussion

The refractive indices and the densities of the following mixed solvents were measured experimentally at the indicate temperatures : (1) protic-protic solvent mixtures (EtOH-PrOH, EtOH-BuOH at 25°C, PrOH-H₂O at 25, 30 and 35°C and PrOH-BuOH at 25°C), (2) aprotic-protic solvent mixtures (DMSO-DMF at 25, 30 and 35°C, DMSO-DI and DMF-DI at 25°C), (3) aprotic-protic solvent mixtures (DMSO-H₂O at 25, 30 and 35°C, DMSO-MeOH, DMSO-EtOH, DMSO-PrOH, DMSO-BuOH, DI-H₂O, DI-MeOH, DI-EtOH, DI-PrOH and DI-BuOH, all at 25°C) .

From the values of the measured refractive indices (n), the values of the excess refractive indices n_E can be calculated⁴ using eq. (1) .

$$n_E = n_{\text{mixture}} - (X_{S1}n_1 + X_{S2}n_2) \quad (1)$$

where X_{S1} , X_{S2} , n_1 and n_2 are the mole fractions by weight and the refractive indices of the first and the second solvents in their mixtures respectively, for example (MeOH(1)–EtOH(2)). The value of n_{mixture} is the refractive index value of the mixed solvents. The values X_{S1} and X_{S2} can be calculated by applying eq. (2).

$$X_{S1} = \frac{\frac{\text{Vol.}\%(1) \times d_1}{M_1}}{\frac{\text{Vol.}\%(1) \times d_1}{M_1} + \frac{\text{Vol.}\%(2) \times d_2}{M_2}} \quad (2)$$

where d_1 , d_2 , M_1 , M_2 , Vol. % (1) and Vol. % (2) are the densities, the molecular weights and the volume percentages of the first and the second solvents respectively. The value of X_{S2} is then equals to $(1 - X_{S1})$.

Also from the values of the measured refractive indices, the molar refraction (R) can be calculated¹ using eq. (3).

$$R = \frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} V = P_A + P_E = P_D = P_T \quad (3)$$

where V is the molar volume which can be calculated by (M/d), where M and d are the molecular weight and the measured density of the pure or the mixed solvents respectively. The molecular weights of the mixed solvents were calculated using eq. (4) .

$$M_{\text{mixture}} = X_{S1} \cdot M_1 + X_{S2} \cdot M_2 \quad (4)$$

The right hand side of eq. (3) is equal to the total molar polarization or the distortion polarization which equal to the summation of both the electron polarization (P_E) and the atomic polarization (P_A). The atomic polarization (P_A) were calculated¹³ from eq. (5).

$$P_A = 1.05n^2 \quad (5)$$

The mean value of the molecular dipole polarizability (α ; dipole moment induced by electric field) can be calculated from the optical refractive index (n) of a material containing N molecules per unit volume. The refractive index is related to the polarizability of the molecules by Lorenz-Lorenz formula¹⁴ as shown in eq. (6).

$$\frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} = \frac{4\pi\bar{n}\alpha}{3} \quad (6)$$

where $\bar{n} = \frac{N}{V}$, N is the Avogadro's number and V is the molar volume. From eq. (6), the polarizabilities of the mixed solvents under investigation were calculated.

The solvated radii of the solvents were calculated using eq. (7) by considering spherical form of the solvated molecules¹⁵.

$$V = \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 \quad (7)$$

The values of the measured refractive indices (n), the excess refractive indices (n_E), the molar refractions (R), the atomic polarization (P_A), the polarizabilities (α), the measured densities (d), the molar volumes (V) and the solvated radii (r), were recorded in Table 1 for the protic-protic solvent mixtures. Table 2 for the aprotic-protic solvent mix-

tures and Table 3 for aprotic-protic solvent mixtures.

The results of the excess refractive indices show that :
(1) For the protic-protic solvent mixtures Fig. 1, the order of decreasing the excess refractive indices were :

* (PrOH-H₂O) at 25°C > (PrOH-H₂O) at 35°C > (PrOH-BuOH) at 25°C > (PrOH-EtOH) at 25°C.

* (EtOH-H₂O)¹⁵ > (EtOH-BuOH) > (EtOH-MeOH)¹⁵ > (EtOH-PrOH) all at 25°C.

(2) For the aprotic-protic solvent mixtures Fig. 2 : the order was :

(DMF-AN)¹⁵ > (DMSO-AN)¹⁵ > (DI-AN)¹⁵ > (DMSO-DI) > (DMF-DI), all at 25°C > (DMSO-DMF)¹⁵ at 25°C > (DMSO-DMF) at 35°C. From this order it was noticed that :

* DMF-AN > DMF-DI > DMF-DMSO.

* DMSO-AN > DMSO-DI > DMSO-DMF.

* DI-AN > DI-DMSO > DI-DMF.

(3) For the aprotic-protic solvent mixtures Figs. 3 and 4 the orders of decreasing the excess refractive indices were :

DMSO-H₂O at 25°C > DMSO-H₂O at 35°C > DMSO-MeOH at 25°C > DMSO-EtOH at 25°C > DMSO-PrOH at 25°C > DMSO-BuOH at 25°C.

DI-H₂O > DI-MeOH > DI-EtOH > DI-PrOH > DI-BuOH, a.

The above results indicating a high solvent-solvent interaction (solvophilic attraction) in the same orders which may be due to the difference in the value of both the dielectric constant and the dipole moment between each pairs of solvent in the mixtures in the same order. The solvent-solvent interaction may also be affected by the ability of the

Table 1. The molar volume (V) ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$), the polarizabilities (α) ($\text{cm}^3/\text{molecule}$) $\times 10^{-24}$ of some protic-protic solvent mixtures

Vol. % of the first solvent	EtOH-PrOH		EtOH-BuOH		PrOH-H ₂ O						PrOH-BuOH	
	25°C		25°C		25°C		30°C		35°C		25°C	
	V	α	V	α	V	α	V	α	V	α	V	α
0	75.78	6.89	91.85	8.82	18.07	1.47	18.13	1.477	18.18	1.479	91.85	8.82
10	73.65	6.68	87.03	8.30	19.57	1.63	19.62	1.627	19.68	1.628	90.01	8.60
20	71.63	6.69	82.50	7.81	21.31	1.81	21.37	1.805	21.44	1.807	88.19	8.39
30	69.69	6.28	78.67	7.40	23.45	2.02	23.47	2.017	23.55	2.017	86.43	8.19
40	67.86	6.09	75.02	7.01	25.98	2.27	26.12	2.275	26.13	2.270	84.75	7.99
50	66.12	5.92	71.67	6.63	29.21	2.58	29.30	2.579	29.34	2.573	83.12	7.80
60	64.44	5.76	68.59	6.29	33.30	2.97	33.40	2.969	33.45	2.963	81.53	7.62
70	62.89	5.61	65.73	5.97	38.70	3.48	38.81	3.471	38.80	3.458	80.00	7.43
80	61.37	5.46	63.27	5.70	42.26	3.84	46.45	4.167	46.64	4.187	78.63	7.26
90	59.93	5.32	60.82	5.43	57.47	5.24	57.67	5.220	59.00	5.316	77.21	7.08
100	58.53	5.18	58.53	5.18	75.78	6.89	76.07	6.890	76.44	6.891	75.78	6.89

Table 2. The molar volume (V) ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$), the polarizabilities (α) ($\text{cm}/\text{molecule}$) $\times 10^{-24}$ of some aprotic-protic solvent mixtures

Vol. % of the first solvent	DMSO-DMF						DMSO-DI		DMF-DI	
	25°C		30°C		35°C		25°C		25°C	
	V	α	V	α	V	α	V	α	V	α
0	77.41	7.36	77.58	7.910	77.77	7.910	85.80	8.60	85.80	8.60
10	76.78	7.93	76.92	7.923	77.07	7.908	84.14	8.59	84.92	8.57
20	76.16	7.95	76.22	7.931	76.45	7.924	82.49	8.52	83.99	8.49
30	75.51	7.96	75.65	7.949	75.84	7.938	80.92	8.46	83.11	8.42
40	74.90	7.97	75.07	7.962	75.22	7.947	79.39	8.40	82.26	8.35
50	74.22	7.96	74.43	7.968	74.61	7.957	77.90	8.33	81.39	8.28
60	73.63	7.97	73.76	7.959	73.99	7.921	76.51	8.26	80.64	8.20
70	73.05	7.97	73.19	7.964	73.32	7.948	75.14	8.19	79.81	8.13
80	72.47	7.97	72.61	7.964	72.74	7.949	73.81	8.11	78.98	8.06
90	71.90	7.97	72.05	7.965	72.17	7.949	72.53	8.03	78.14	7.98
100	71.30	7.90	71.45	7.961	71.61	7.950	71.30	7.90	77.41	7.36

Table 3. The molar volume (V) ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$), the polarizabilities (α) ($\text{cm}/\text{molecule}$) $\times 10^{-24}$ of some aprotic-protic solvent mixtures

Vol. % of the first solvent	DMSO-H ₂ O				DMSO-MeOH		DMSO-EtOH		DMSO-PrOH			
	25°C		30°C		35°C		25°C		25°C			
	V	α	V	α	V	α	V	α	V	α		
0	18.07	1.470	18.13	1.477	18.18	1.479	40.73	3.27	58.53	4.81	75.78	6.42
10	19.67	1.680	19.60	1.666	19.65	1.663	43.20	3.62	59.97	5.45	75.14	7.01
20	21.54	1.900	21.31	1.872	21.38	1.871	45.79	3.99	61.37	5.72	74.55	7.13
30	23.75	2.180	23.36	2.140	23.44	2.140	48.48	4.37	62.71	5.99	74.02	7.24
40	26.40	2.490	25.84	2.422	25.92	2.418	51.33	4.79	64.03	6.28	73.55	7.35
50	29.68	2.880	28.92	2.797	29.03	2.801	54.23	5.23	65.32	6.55	73.10	7.46
60	33.76	3.399	32.80	3.289	32.93	3.288	57.36	5.72	66.58	6.83	72.69	7.57
70	39.03	4.056	37.92	3.927	38.10	3.933	60.63	6.23	67.83	7.11	72.34	7.67
80	46.07	4.934	45.01	4.803	45.17	4.802	63.97	6.77	69.01	7.40	71.93	7.78
90	56.18	6.153	55.27	6.035	55.35	6.025	67.61	7.35	70.19	7.69	71.64	7.87
100	71.30	7.900	71.45	7.968	71.61	7.975	71.30	7.90	71.30	7.90	71.30	7.90

Vol. % of the first solvent	DMSO-BuOH		DI-H ₂ O		DI-MeOH		DI-EtOH		DI-PrOH		DI-BuOH	
	25°C		30°C		35°C		25°C		25°C		25°C	
	V	α	V	α	V	α	V	α	V	α	V	α
0	91.85	8.82	18.07	1.37	40.73	3.05	58.53	4.81	75.78	6.42	91.85	8.817
10	89.37	8.76	19.53	1.64	42.84	3.53	60.34	5.41	76.51	7.05	91.16	8.797
20	86.97	8.69	21.43	1.87	45.50	3.86	62.49	5.68	77.63	7.23	90.61	8.794
30	84.62	8.61	23.71	2.09	48.39	4.20	64.78	5.97	78.63	7.39	90.01	8.783
40	82.43	8.53	26.49	2.39	51.75	4.59	67.23	6.28	81.45	7.74	89.45	8.776
50	80.34	8.44	29.85	2.75	55.22	5.02	69.62	6.59	80.63	7.74	88.81	8.758
60	78.38	8.36	34.39	3.23	59.58	5.53	72.43	6.95	81.52	7.92	88.21	8.736
70	76.54	8.26	40.49	3.88	64.68	6.13	75.42	7.32	82.71	8.09	87.69	8.723
80	74.70	8.16	48.99	4.78	70.31	6.81	78.55	7.72	83.71	8.27	86.98	8.687
90	72.99	8.06	62.57	6.20	77.54	7.66	82.04	8.17	84.77	8.46	86.43	8.669
100	71.30	7.90	85.80	8.60	85.80	8.60	85.80	8.60	85.80	8.60	85.80	8.600

Fig. 1. The excess refractive index n_E versus the mole fraction (X_2) for : (a) (EtOH-PrOH), (b) (EtOH-BuOH) at 25°C, (c) (PrOH-H₂O) at 25°C, (c^{||}) (PrOH-H₂O) at 35°C, (d) (PrOH-BuOH) at 25°C, (e) (EtOH-H₂O) at 25°C and (f) (EtOH-MeOH), all at 25°C.

Fig. 3. The excess refractive index n_E versus the mole fraction (X_2) for : (a) (DMSO-H₂O) at 25°C, (a^{||}) (DMSO-H₂O) at 35°C, (b) (DMSO-MeOH), (c) (DMSO-EtOH), (d) (DMSO-PrOH) and (e) (DMSO-BuOH), all at 25°C.

Fig. 2. The excess refractive index n_E versus the mole fraction (X_2) for : (a) (DMSO-DMF) at 25°C, (a^{||}) (DMSO-DMF) at 35°C, (b) (DMSO-DI), (c) (DMF-DI), (d) (DMF-AN), (e) (DI-AN) and (f) (DMSO-AN), all at 25°C.

Fig. 4. The excess refractive index n_E versus the mole fraction (X_2) for : (a) (DI-H₂O), (b) (DI-MeOH), (c) (DI-EtOH), (d) (DI-PrOH) and (e) (DI-BuOH), all at 25°C.

solvents to form hydrogen bonds with each others. Also this may be related to the donor number order as reported by Marcus¹⁷ as follows : DMF > DMSO > DI > PrOH > EtOH > AN > MeOH. It also concluded that the solvophilic attraction follow the order as in the given figures.

In comparing the solvent-solvent interaction process in

the case of aprotic-protic, protic-protic and aprotic-protic solvent mixtures Fig. 5, the results show that the order of decreasing the interaction is :

DMSO-H₂O > (DMF-H₂O)¹⁵ > DI-H₂O > (AN-H₂O)¹⁸ all at 25°C as aprotic-protic solvent mixtures.

PrOH-H₂O > (EtOH-H₂O)¹⁵ > (MeOH-H₂O)¹⁸ all at 25°C as aprotic-protic solvent mixtures.

DMSO-AN > DMSO-DI > DMSO-DMF all at 25°C as

Fig. 5. The excess refractive index versus the mol fraction for : (a) (DMSO-H₂O), (b) (DMF-H₂O), (c) (AN-H₂O), (d) (MeOH-H₂O) and (DMSO-AN), (e) (EtOH-H₂O), (f) (PrOH-H₂O), (g) (DI-H₂O), (h) (DMSO-DMF) and (DMSO-DI), all at 25°C.

aprotic-aprotic solvent mixtures. As all, DMSO-H₂O > (DMF-H₂O)¹⁵ > DI-H₂O > PrOH-H₂O > (EtOH-H₂O)¹⁵

(MeOH-H₂O)¹⁸ ≈ (DMSO-AN)¹⁵ > DMSO-DI ≈ DMSO-DMF.

This indicates that the solvent-solvent interaction has the highest value in the case of DMSO-H₂O system. This also indicates that the solvent-solvent interaction in the case of aprotic-protic solvent mixtures is higher than that in the case of the protic-protic and the aprotic-aprotic ones. This may be due to the differences in the values of the dielectric constant, the dipole moment and the donor number of the above solvents.

The same order was approximately involved for the other aprotic-protic solvent mixtures under investigation except DMF, where the order was : DMF-used alcohols > DMSO-alcohols > DI-alcohols > AN-alcohols.

The volume and the weight percentage were determined at which maximum values of the excess refractive indices for each mixed system were achieved. These maximum values indicates the high solvent-solvent interaction depend mainly on the different physical properties of the solvent such as the dielectric constant, the dipole moment, the donor number and the chemical structure. The values of the volume and the weight percentage referred to the maximum excess refractive indices are recorded in Table 4. As shown from this Table, we can choose or define the suitable composition of any mixture under investigation which has maximum excess refractive index value and so maximum sol-

Table 4. The volume percentages and the weight percentages of the first solvent at which maximum excess refractive indices were recorded for many mixtures at 25°C

Mixtures	Vol. %	Wt. %
Protic-protic mixtures		
EtOH-PrOH at 25°C	40	46.2
EtOH-BuOH at 25°C	40	51.1
PrOH-H ₂ O at 25, 30 and 35°C	60	26.4
PrOH-BuOH at 25°C	60	64.8
Aprotic-aprotic mixtures		
DMSO-DMF at 25, 30 and 35°C	50	59
DMSO-DI at 25°C	50	58
DMF-DI at 25°C	50	62
Aprotic-protic mixtures		
DMSO-H ₂ O at 25, 30 and 35°C	70	37.1
DMSO-MeOH at 25°C	60	46.2
DMSO-EtOH at 25°C	40	35.4
DMSO-PrOH at 25°C	50	51.5
DMSO-BuOH at 25°C	50	56.5
DI-H ₂ O at 25°C	70	33.1
DI-MeOH at 25°C	60	41.7
DI-EtOH at 25°C	50	40.6
DI-PrOH at 25°C	50	47.2
DI-BuOH at 25°C	50	51.8

vent-solvent interaction.

The calculated values of the molar refractions, the atomic polarizations, the polarizabilities, the molecular volumes and the solvated radii show a reverse order to that of the previously mentioned excess refractive indices. This means that, as the excess refractive index increases, the solvent-solvent interaction increase and on the contrary, the molar refraction, the polarizability, the atomic polarization, the molar volume and the solvated radii are decreased.

Effect of temperature :

The results show that, the measured refractive indices, the excess refractive indices illustrated in Figs. 1-3. The calculated atomic polarization and the densities of some mixtures under investigation [(PrOH-H₂O), (DMSO-DMF) and (DMSO-H₂O)], were found to be decreased as the temperature increased, because the solvophilic interaction (electrostatic interaction) can be decreased by increasing temperature. The effective composition for which maximum excess refractive indices is obtained, was not altered with temperature (Table 4).

On the other hand, the values of the molar refractions, the molar volumes and the solvent-solvent solvated radii were increased as the temperature increased.

Conclusions :

The excess refractive indices and so the solvent-solvent interaction process depends on the nature of solvent and on its physical properties such as the dielectric constant, the dipole moment and the donor number.

The maximum excess refractive indices indicates maximum solvent-solvent interaction process and so define the suitable solvent with high effective properties (Table 4), for example (EtOH -H₂O) system .

Experimental

The used methanol (MeOH), absolute ethanol (EtOH), propanol (PrOH) and butanol (BuOH) are from Adwic Co. Dimethylformamide (DMF), acetonitrile (AN), dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) and 1,4-dioxane (DI) solvents were supplied from Aldrich Chemical Co.

The different mixtures (from 0–100% vol.%) of the used solvents were prepared in a clean and dry test tubes which closed carefully. The mixed solvents were kept in a thermostated water bath of the type (Clifton) for a period of 30 minutes at the choosed temperature degree. The refractive indices of the prepared mixtures were measured using (Abbe's refractometer) which connected with ultra-thermostate of type (Kottermann 4130). The densities were also measured for the prepared mixtures using a weighing bottle (1 ml).

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